

Rethinking the use of antimicrobials in livestock production systems

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Intensive Danish pig farming faces structural lock-ins for achieving a prudent AMU

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This contributes to the objective of identifying levers and lock-ins for adherence to prudent use principles in the use of antibiotics in animal farming.

The European Union is the world's second largest pork producer, and the majority is produced as bulk meat in intensive farming systems.

This policy brief should be particularly interesting for policy-makers and stakeholders, as well as researchers and professionals interested in structures affecting the farming systems and their ability to change.

OVERVIEW

The yearly use of antibiotics in Danish pigs reaches 72.3 kg of active compound. Thus, despite being considered as a frontrunner country in terms of prudent use of antibiotics in animals, there is still room for improvement. Based on stakeholder interviews and experiences from the Danish pig living lab, we identified how structural constraints are lock-ins for change.

Actors in Danish pig farming have a high level of knowledge of factors that influence the need for antibiotics. The project brought forward how achieving a low use of antibiotics is not “rocket science” but a matter of good husbandry and investment in housing and management that support health. Several structural constraints in nowadays Danish pig farming, however, were noted to prevent pigs from being managed in a way that supports health and prevents unnecessary use of antibiotics. These constraints include sows bred for hyper prolificacy, problems with staff recruitment, and low profits on a competitive global market. The problems are intertwined. Sows giving birth to more piglets than they can nurse and to many underweight piglets necessitate an extensive use of nursing sows and much supportive work by the staff. Thus, Danish pig farming is in its essence extremely dependent on competent farm workers. However, when educated staff is lacking and training of staff is complicated by language difficulties, problems are handled with antibiotics. Within the existing breeding regime and without financial room for investment in staff and improved conditions to prevent disease, serious efforts to reduce the need for antibiotics are not done.

RELATED PROJECT OUTPUTS

- National Pig Conference, developed material [in Danish]
- Report [in Danish]: ‘Antibiotics in the Danish pig production – agreements and disagreements among actors’ [Holdninger til brug af antibiotika i den danske svineproduktion samlet i ny rapport \(au.dk\)](#)

RESULTS

Knowledge transfer

The project identified that employees in pig farms are often immigrant workers who came to Denmark with no skills in farming and in many cases with a low level of English language. Knowledge about how to farm with a low need for antibiotics is difficult to transfer to these key stakeholders. Despite the fact that these persons often are the ones to take daily decisions on treatment, they are not involved in the discussions about management and disease prevention on the farms and therefore do not actively engage in how things are done.

Dissemination Activities

The project emphasized the importance of transdisciplinary exchange and multistakeholder engagement in order to facilitate change. We arranged a multistakeholder meeting on four themes: “Antibiotics and resistance”, “Consumers, citizens and antibiotics”, “Using antibiotics and alternatives” and “Breeding for robust pigs – is that the way forward?”. The aim of the meeting was to point out where do actors agree and disagree on these subjects. A report with the title “Antibiotics in the Danish pig production - agreements and disagreements among actors was published[in Danish]

Homogenize standards and regulations

The project pointed out the complexity of the farming landscape in relation to antibiotic usage. Attempts to solve complex structural issues consumer-driven alternatives and farm-directed limits on antibiotic usage primarily target farmers and vets and do not take into account how decision-making in farming is influenced by a variety of dependencies.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Employees need formal education and training in the management of pigs and prevention of disease. Furthermore, they need language skills that enable them to contribute in the daily discussions and decision-making in order to avoid routine treatment and over-treatment.

Reasons why the employee situation in pig farming is so difficult need to be clarified and acted upon.

Continue multistakeholder dialogues to foster mutual understanding and collected action towards more prudent AMU.

Because the discussions in the Danish Pig Living Lab made clear that a reduction of AMU in intensive pig farming cannot be handled by individuals or organisations – structural changes and political governance are imperative. These structural changes must be initiated and followed by multiactor involvement.

Structural problems need structural solutions, legislation and good governance should ensure this.

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